

RESULTS OF PLASMA ANTI-SARS-COV-2 BLOOD DONOR INVESTIGATION FOR THE TREATMENT OF COVID-19 PATIENTS

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Abstract

Introduction. Currently, COVID-19 treatment includes several options, including the use of convalescent plasma. In this context, the presence of anti-SARS-CoV-2 in blood donors after the clinical recovery of COVID-19 depending on the place of residence, age and the clinical manifestation of the disease is of scientific-practical interest.

The aim of the study: is to investigate how the use of blood plasma from people who have been cured of COVID-19 and given to critically ill patients can give them an immune boost.

Material and methods. A total of 119 donors were examined from patients - 18-60 years old males with a history of COVID-19 disease, PCR confirmed case, cured with negative result for COVID-19 in a PCR test and at least 14 days after clinical recovery. The presence / absence of anti-SARS-CoV-2 was assessed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay.

Conclusion. The study shows that male blood donors aged 18-60 years, with a confirmed history of disease, later cured, positive for the presence of anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG can serve as a source of fresh plasma used for the treatment of COVID patients. -19, especially with severe clinical manifestations of the disease.

Keywords: COVID-19; plasma; anti-SARS-CoV-2; donors; PCR test; immune response

Introduction

Many options for treating COVID-19 are currently being explored. These include new medicines specifically designed to target SARS-CoV-2, as well as existing medicines designed to treat another disease. Conventionally these drugs can be classified as follows:

- Treatments with good results (dexamethasone, remdesivir) (6, 7, 11, 12, 13, 30, 31)
- Promising treatments (convalescent plasma, monoclonal antibodies, Famipirovir, interferon) (1, 2, 3, 8, 9, 28, 29)
- Treatments in the early stages of studies (ivermectin, MK-4482, ACE protein, blood purification, anticoagulants) (10, 11, 13, 14)

At the same time, it should be noted that the latest information from the WHO based on a study conducted in about 30 countries shows that medicinal products: Remdesivir, hydroxychlorixin, Lopinavir / Ritonovir

and interferons do not indicate an obvious effect on hospital mortality on reducing mortality.

By far, however, the oldest treatment tested is convalescent plasma. This involves the use of blood plasma from people who have been cured of COVID-19 and its administration to patients who currently have the disease. Plasma transfused to patients who are in a serious and extremely serious condition provides a boost to the immune system, thus favoring the acceleration of the recovery process. The use of convalescent plasma involves the transfer of antibodies from patients who already have an immune response, thus providing separate (but transient) protection to the recipient (1, 2, 3).

Plasma collected and filtered from patients who had COVID-19 could help other patients because it has antibodies developed by those who were cured. The treatment is old and is used in other diseases, including the flu, but studies for COVID-19 are just beginning.

An early study of 39 patients concluded that convalescent plasma could be an effective treatment, especially for patients who are not intubated (26). A study of 136 patients showed a reduction in mortality (compared to those who did not receive plasma) if treatment was given early and antibody levels were higher (27). On the other hand, a Dutch study was stopped prematurely when it was found that there was no improvement in those receiving plasma and that patients developed antibodies without this treatment anyway (25).

There are some major issues in determining the effectiveness of this treatment. Plasma harvesting from those who had COVID-19 is cumbersome, antibody levels vary from patient to patient, so there is no standard plasma. Doctors at the Mayo Clinic tracked the progress of more than 35,000 patients who received convalescent plasma, mostly in the critical stages of the disease (24). The conclusion of the observation is that patients receiving convalescent plasma treatment three days after diagnosis have a lower risk of death (21.7% after 30 days) than those receiving four days or more (26.7%).) and that treatment may be more effective if plasma antibody levels are higher. However, the lack of a control group makes the conclusions less relevant, and plasma remains at the stage of "experimental treatment" at least in the USA (7).

In the Republic of Moldova, convalescent plasma is approved and recommended for patients who develop severe clinical forms of COVID-19 (20).

In this context, the results of the study on the investigation of plasma from blood donors after the clinical recovery of COVID-19, the presence / absence of anti-SARS-CoV-2 depending on age, place of residence and lifestyle are of particular scientific and practical interest. clinical manifestation of the nominated infection.

Material and methods

A total of 119 donors were examined from patients (presumably tested for the absence of markers of blood-borne infections: viral hepatitis B, C and D and HIV), from different administrative territories of the Republic

of Moldova (17, 18, 19, 20). Patients included males, aged 18-60 years, with a history of COVID-19 disease, confirmed case, cured (complete resolution of symptoms) and a negative result for COVID-19 in a PCR test and at least 14 days after clinical recovery.

The PCR test was performed using Applied Biosystems USA equipment and consumables as follows, RIBO, Russia (extraction kit) and N-CoV (China) amplification kit.

ELISA enzyme immunoassay for the identification of anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG was performed using ELISA, Generic Assays GmbH (Germany).

The statistical processing of the obtained results was performed with the help of the programs: SPSS Statistics for Windows, version 20 and Microsoft Excel 2019, with the application of the set of statistical programs SPSS v 18.0, Quanto v1.2, Review manager (RevMan) v 5.1, GMDR Beta software 0.9.

Results and discussions

The 119 donors of convalescent plasma by age were distributed as follows: dominated by people aged 26 to 45 years, in a lower percentage were donors aged 18-25 years and 46-60 years. Of the total number of donors - 104 (87.4%) demonstrated the presence of anti-SARS-CoV-2, IgG class, and 15 (12.6%) found no antibodies. Donors identified positively for the presence of anti-SARS-CoV-2 in age dependence were distributed as follows: 18-25 years (12.5%), 26-35 years (37.5%), 36-45 years (28 , 8%) and 46-60 years (21.2%). A higher incidence of identifying the presence of nominated antibodies was determined in plasma patients aged 26-45 years ($p = 0.01$). This phenomenon can probably be explained by the fact that the process of immunogenesis of anti-SARS-CoV-2 formation in this age group is more active compared to what happens in older people - 60 years (15) .

The analysis of the absence of anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG in the age groups shows that practically these indicators by value in the statistically nominated age groups do not differ ($p \geq 0.05$), although in the age group 46-60 years shows a downward trend in this indicator, probably to argue this finding requires further studies with the accumulation of a larger number of plasma donors.

Table 1

Results of plasma donor investigation of anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG by ELISA

Age (years)			Presence anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG				Absence anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG			
			of the total number of donors		from the number of positive ones		of the total number of donors		from the number of negative ones	
years	abs.	P±ES	abs.	P±ES	abs.	P±ES	abs.	P±ES	abs.	%
18-25	18	15,1±3,3	13	10,9±2,9	13	12,5±3,2	5	4,2±1,8	5	33,3
26-35	44	37,0±4,4	39	32,8±4,3	39	37,5±4,7	5	4,2±1,8	5	33,3
36-45	33	27,7±4,1	30	25,2±4,0	30	28,8±4,4	3	2,5±1,4	3	20,0
46-60	24	20,2±3,7	22	18,5±3,6	22	21,2±4,0	2	1,7±1,2	2	13,4
18-60	119	100,0	119	87,4±3,0	104	100,0	15	12,6	15	100,0

Depending on the place of residence, the donors were as follows: urban - 90 (75.6%) and rural 29 (24.4%), urban donors predominate ($p = 0.001$), probably these circumstances can be explained by the higher level of information from the Public Medico-Sanitary Institutions, have access to various media sources and to public transport to travel to the donation points. Moreover, the majority of patients and donors who contracted the disease and recovered came from urban areas (16). The share of donors depending on the clinical

manifestation of COVID-19 infection was as follows: pathologies with mild clinical forms (acute viral respiratory infections) - 73 (61.3%), average clinical form (acute laryngotracheitis, acute bronchitis, acute rhinopharyngitis) - 36 (30.3%) and severe forms (severe bilateral pneumonia) - 10 (8.4%). It should be noted that plasma donors tested negative for the presence of anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG did not find donors with severe clinical manifestations of the disease (Table 2).

Table 2

Distribution of convalescent plasma donors by place of residence, form of clinical manifestation of COVID-19 infection, and presence / absence of anti-SARS-CoV-2

Evaluation indicators	Place of residence				Clinical form of COVID-19 infection						Anti-SARS-CoV-2			
	urban		rural		easy		medium		sever		present		absent	
	abs.	P±ES	abs.	P±ES	abs.	P±ES	abs.	P±ES	abs.	P±ES	abs.	P±ES	abs.	P±ES
Place of residence Severity of the disease Presence / absence of anti-SARS-CoV-2	90	95,6±3,9	29	24,4±3,9	73	61,3±4,5	36	30,3±4,2	10	8,4±2,5	104	87,4±3,0	15	12,6±3,0

The data on the distribution of convalescent plasma donors with anti-SARS-CoV-2 by age of residence and the form of clinical manifestation of the infection reflected in Table 3 are of scientific and practical interest.

Table 3

Distribution of convalescent plasma donors with anti-SARS-CoV-2 by age, place of residence and clinical manifestation of COVID-19 infection

Evaluation indicators	age			Place of residence				Clinical form of COVID-19 infection						
	ani	abs.	P±ES	urban		rural		easy		medium		sever		
				abs.	P±ES	abs.	P±ES	abs.	P±ES	abs.	P±ES	abs.	P±ES	
Age	18-25	13	12,5±3,2											
Place of residence	26-35	39	37,5±4,7	78	75,0±4,2	26	25,0±4,2	63	60,6±4,8	31	29,8±4,5	10	9,6±2,9	
Severity of the disease	36-45	30	28,8±4,4											
	46-60	22	21,2±4,0											

Depending on age, convalescent plasma donors are distributed as follows: 18-25 years (12.5%); 26-35 (37.5%); 36-45 (28.8%); 46-60 years -21.2%. The data presented show that the share of anti-SARS-CoV-2 donors who donated convalescent plasma was higher in the 26-35 (37.5%) and 36-45 (28.8%) age groups compared to age group 18-25 years (12.5%) ($P = 0.01$). This difference can be partly explained by the fact that the incidence of COVID-19 in the Republic of Moldova is increased among people aged 26-45 (16).

The share of plasma donors with anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG depending on the clinical form of the disease was as follows: mild (acute viral respiratory infections) - 63 (60.6%); moderate (acute laryngotracheitis, acute bronchitis, acute rhinopharyngitis) - 31 (29.8%) and severe (severe bilateral pneumonia) - 10 (9.6%). Analyzing the results reflected in Table 3 we find that in plasma donors, positive for the presence of anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG dominated the mild form of clinical manifestation

of the disease (60.6%), followed by the average form 29.8%. The severe form of COVID-19 infection in plasma donors was 9.6%, which can be partly explained by the lower incidence of clinical manifestations of COVID-19 infection compared to moderate and severe forms.

The distribution of negative convalescent plasma donors in the presence of anti-SARS-CoV-2 by age, place of residence, and clinical manifestation of COVID-19 infection shows that there is no statistically significant difference between age groups ($p \geq 0, p \geq 0, 05$). According to the place of residence, the share of urban donors is higher than those of rural areas, circumstances possibly clarified by the absolute domination of urban donors, but for relevant conclusions additional studies are required. Of interest is the share of absent donors in the presence of anti-SARS-CoV-2 depending on the form of clinical manifestation of COVID-19 infection (Table 4).

Table 4.

Distribution of negative convalescent plasma donors in the presence of anti-SARS-CoV-2 by age, place of residence and clinical manifestation of COVID-19 infection

Evaluation indicators	age			Place of residence				Clinical form of COVID-19 infection					
	ani	abs.	P± ES	urban		rural		easy		medium		sever	
				abs.	P± ES	abs.	P± ES	abs.	P± ES	abs.	P± ES	abs.	P± ES
Age	18-25	5	33,3±12,2										
Place of residence	26-35	5	33,3±12,2	12	80,0±10,3	3	20,0±10,3	10	66,7±12,1	5	33,3±12,2	-	-
Severity of the dise	36-45	3	20,0±10,3										
	46-61	2	13,3±8,7										

Note: Donors with a negative clinical manifestation of severe anti-SARS-CoV-2 convalescent plasma have not been identified.

The mild clinical form was identified in 10 donors, and the mean clinical form in 5 donors, it is important to note that the severe form of COVID-19 was not identified in donors tested negative for anti-SARS-CoV-2. These data probably suggest the idea that severe forms of the disease induce the production of anti-SARS-CoV-2 in a much higher percentage compared to mild and moderate forms, but even in this situation additional studies are required (15). It is worth noting the data showing that in 40 convalescent plasma donors, who donated repeatedly after 8-25 days, it was found that the reference indices of plasma samples tested in dynamics (repeated) expressed by the cut-off value, negative result, equivocal and positive in ELISA, practically do not differ, which shows that in patients with COVID-19 after recovery anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG is maintained, but to identify the deadline for identification of the nominated antibodies requires further monitoring of this phenomenon.

Similar results were obtained by other researchers [21, 22], who demonstrated in a group of 34 patients (initially confirmed in the presence of SARS-CoV-2 by PCR), where the majority of participants had a mild clinical form (20 women and 14 men). With an average age of 43 years (range 21-68). A total of 31 of the 34 participants had two serial measurements of IgG levels, and the remaining 3 participants had three serial measurements. Blood samples in the presence of anti-SARS-CoV-2 were analyzed by ELISA, able to identify the concentration of antibodies.

The first measurement was obtained at an average of 37 days after the onset of symptoms, and the last measurement after 86 days after the onset of symptoms. The mean initial IgG level was 3.48 log 10 ng per milliliter (range 2.52-4.41).

Subsequently, based on a linear regression model, which included the age and sex of the participants, the days from the onset of symptoms to the first measurement and the first level of antibodies detected, it was shown that the estimated mean change (slope) was 0.0062, which corresponds to a half-life of approximately 36 days in the observation period of up to 100 days. Compared to the titer of antibodies developed by SARS-CoV-1 virus, it is probably shorter and the period of identification of IgG in the blood for SARS-

CoV-2 is shorter, a fact found by the authors in question as a result of a comparable exponential assessment of dynamics of reducing the concentration of IgG class antibodies. These circumstances raise concerns that the humoral immunity developed against SARS-CoV-2 virus infection may not be lasting in people with mild clinical forms of Covid-19.

The results obtained require caution in identifying the shelf life of IgG antibodies in the plasma, the protection threshold, the duration of immunity, the possibility of using "passports of immunity" based on the level of antibodies and consequently the durability of the vaccine.

Studies by other scientists [23] in a group of 750 patients have shown that anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG remain in the body for more than 100 days after it occurs. This type of antibody was measured in former Covid-19 patients at stable levels for up to 105 days against IgM and IgA whose concentration begins to decrease after 30 days. The authors point out that there is no definite information about the level of protection they could provide against a potential reinfection, but conclude that an effective vaccine would demonstrate a lasting immune response. One study tries to show that the level of antibodies in saliva correlates with that in the blood, which opens up the possibility of using alternative tests. The analysis with the information presented shows that further studies are needed to define the duration of anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG in plasma, the protection threshold, the rate of decline (half-life) of antibodies in serum, their concentration depending on the clinical form. manifestation of the disease, extremely important data not only for the blood service, but also for strengthening the control measures and response to Covid-19 infection, including by identifying the indicators of seroprevalence, duration of immunity, protection threshold, etc.

Conclusions:

1. The data obtained show that practically 87.4% of plasma donors responded to COVID-19 infection by the expression of anti-SARS-CoV-2, IgG with a predominance in the age group 26-35 years.

2. Most donors made the clinical form mild and moderate, which can be explained by the presentation of potentially healthy plasma donors without chronic

concomitant disease with COVID-19. No link has been identified between the degree of moderate or mild clinical manifestation of the disease and the presence or absence of anti-SARS-CoV-2.

3. It is important to note that all severe clinical forms of COVID-19 infection have been accompanied by the formation of anti-SARS-CoV-2, IgG.

4. The proportion of anti-SARS-CoV-2 donors who donated convalescent plasma was higher in the 26-35 (37.5%) and 36-45 (28.8%) age groups compared to the age - 18-25 years (12.5%).

5. Urban living environment (75.0%) predominates among convalescent plasma donors, indicating that they are better informed by medical institutions, have access to various media sources and public transport to travel to donation points.

6. The study shows that blood donors - males aged 18-60 years, with a history of COVID-19 disease, etiologically confirmed, subsequently cured with a negative result (PCR) at least 14 days after fresh plasma used for the treatment of COVID-19 patients may be used for clinical recovery, especially with severe (severe and very severe) clinical manifestations of the disease.

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